

NEON -Next Generation Integrated Energy Services for Citizen Energy Communities

WP 2 - Contractual and financial aspects of cross-service integration

D2.3 Service financial structure and business risk distribution

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Executive summary

Deliverable 2.3 is responsible for conducting the analysis and identification of suitable financial structures that will ensure cost effectiveness of the service offer and minimize, at the same time, the business risk for the involved actors.

The workflow was divided between desk analysis conducted by involved partners and an evaluation of shared experiences, best practices, and key challenges in creating and developing renewable energy communities, with a focus on the economic sustainability of projects and financial solutions adopted to support building energy efficiency, renewable energy, and digital innovation. This has been done thanks to two capacity building and engagement workshops, involving sister projects, technology providers, grid stakeholders, service providers, public and private investors.

The results of the report will be used as input for the following WP2 tasks, as well as WP4, WP5 and WP6 tasks and will help in focusing the service offer and setting the foundation of contractual and business models to be elaborated further in the project. In addition, results will be reflected in the specification of legal and financial requirements for the deployment of the proposed service concepts.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

AC	Alternate Current
APPA	Asociación de Empresas de Energías Renovables
B-Corp	Certified B Corporation
BDO	Binder Dijker Otte
BRW	Borrower - Specific
CAPEX	Capital Expenditures
CEC	Citizen Energy Community
CRS	Country - Specific
DC	Direct Current
DPM	Data Management Platform
DR	Demand-Response
EC	European Commission

EEEF	European Energy Efficiency Fund
EEM	Energy Efficient Mortgage
EEMI	Energy Efficient Mortgages Initiative
EPC	Energy Performance Contracting
ESCO	Energy Service Company
ESG	Environmental, Social, Governance
EU	European Union
EV	Electric Vehicles
GEFF	Green Economy Financing Facility
IDAE	Instituto para la Diversificación y Ahorro de la Energía / Institute for Energy Diversification and Saving
IoT	Internet of Things
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M&V	Measurement and Verification

O&M	Operation & Maintenance
P4P	Pay For Performance
PA	Public Administration
PF4EE	Private Finance for Energy Efficiency
PPA	Power Purchase Agreement
PPCP	Public Administration + Private Company + Local Community
PSR	Project -specific
PSRS	Project – category Specific
RE	Renewable Energy
RES	Renewable Energy Source
SIF	Sustainable Investment Forum (WP leader)
SRI	Smart Readiness Indicator
SENS	STEAG Solar Energy Solutions

TPF	Third Party Financing
VES	Virtual Energy Solutions
VPP	Virtual Power Plant

1. Introduction

NEON project aims at developing and establishing a technical and business ecosystem for integrated energy services for European energy communities. These entities shall be capable of **saving energy, reducing CO₂ emissions, and bringing economic and social benefits** while valorising the energy efficiency and flexibility at demand-side. The project will engage network stakeholders, service providers and final consumers to establish, by a co-creation process, the cross-sectoral arrangements and underlying service concepts.

NEON objectives are aligned with the Directive (EU) 2019/944 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 on common rules for the internal market for electricity. This market has been progressively implemented throughout the Union since 1999. The aim is to **deliver practical solutions to contribute to new business opportunities, competitive prices, high standards for services and to the security of supply and sustainability for EU customers** (citizens or businesses).

The Directive (EU) 2019/944 introduced the **Citizen Energy Communities (CECs)** concept as a category of cooperation of citizens or local actors that should be subject to recognition and protection under the European law with the aim to **enable faster market uptake, and facilitate communities, both residential and non-residential, in becoming energy efficient, thanks to the P4P contracts, smart contracts and different agreements that could be reached internally within each of the communities.** In NEON, the CECs service concepts and business models will be showcased in 4 CEC setups (BERCHIDDA in Italy, DOMAINE DE LA SOURCE in France, POLÍGONO INDUSTRIAL LAS CABEZAS in Spain and STAINS CITY in France) serving as early adopters, whereby follow-up replication plans across 7 “follower” communities will be developed during the project.

The analysis carried out in the project shows that **Europe is increasingly committed to empowering consumers to foster energy transition**, recognized as a key element to ensure energy independence and reach the climate goals of the Union. Renewable energy communities bring the following benefits: improved energy security, lower energy bills, active local participation, capacity to influence the cost and the quality of services, and boost local investments. Their role has become even more relevant as a result of the current energy crisis in Europe, which calls for an acceleration of the energy transition and greater energy independence. In this context, it is important to stress the role of energy communities in addressing energy poverty, in order to include disadvantaged households and individuals to enable their access to affordable clean energy. There is **room for improvement to fully unlock the energy efficiency and flexibility potential** of consumers communities, as **crucial subject to drive the transition**: a developing framework needs to set out feasible solutions and best practices to be shared, on contractual and financial aspects.

2. Document objectives and structure

As mentioned above, NEON aims to deliver next-generation integrated energy services for Citizen Energy Communities. For this reason, the **project overall concept was defined to maximise the impact of traditional energy efficiency services**, through holistic optimization of building operation and energy asset utilisation. By doing this, NEON aims to enable integration of:

- **Energy efficiency services** for multi-measure building efficiency improvement (Energy Performance Contracting - EPC/Energy Service Company - ESCo);
- **Optimal energy asset scheduling** (exploiting Renewable Energy Sources - RES, storage and EV charging) for improved self-sufficiency, Virtual Power Plant (VPP)/Virtual Energy Solutions (VES);

- **Demand response services** for grid flexibility improvement;
- **Advanced building control** for optimal operation of heating/cooling systems, lighting, smart appliances, etc.;
- **Use-tailored services** (e.g., scheduling of EV charging or smart appliance control).

This report is targeted to conduct the analysis and identification of suitable financial structures that will ensure cost-effectiveness of the service offer and minimize, at the same time, the business risk for the involved actors.

The main focus was on actual and expected costs in the pilot areas, in order to identify suitable financial structures to **ensure pre-financing of initial energy efficiency interventions and payback** through identified revenue streams. The task workflow was strengthened involving **financial experts and stakeholders, as well as experts from NEON related projects**, analysing how to attract private capital under the concept of CECs. The report is wrapped up by a **set of guidelines for business risk distribution and minimization**.

3. Actual and potential financing schemes

As showed in D2.1, Legal and financial framework for cross-service integration, over the past years the financial community has been encouraged to take a path towards sustainable finance in order to align with the commitment of governments, companies and investors towards net-zero emissions by 2050.

Identifying a sustainable investment universe comes with some hurdles, that will be analysed in chapters 5 and 6. Nevertheless, the offer of financial instruments to support energy efficiency, energy services and energy communities is wide.

The analysis of legal and financial framework for cross-service integration carried out in D2.1 analysed several financial opportunities to support investments in energy efficiency services, optimal energy asset scheduling, demand-response services for grid flexibility improvement, and advanced building control. On one hand, public funding opportunities such as EU funding programs (Recovery and Resilience Facility, Cohesion policy funds, Modernisation Fund, Invest EU, Horizon Europe, etc.), or public-private funding opportunities (European Energy Efficiency Fund (EEEF), Private Finance for Energy Efficiency (PF4EE), Green Economy Financing Facility (GEFF)). On the other hand, private funding opportunities such as soft loans, green mortgages, investments funds, crowdfunding, or on-bill financing schemes in the form of EPCs. With these new funding opportunities, greater support for the circular economy would be encouraged, in addition to not being necessary to participate in European projects, but to be able to rely directly on companies that are interested in the transition to a more efficient and sustainable energy model. In addition, the support to the projects by private companies would help to give more visibility to the energy communities and therefore, they would receive greater support of citizens. Next paragraphs will focus on private financial structures potentially capable of ensuring cost-effectiveness of the service offer and minimizing, at the same time, the business risk for the involved actors. During the Task period, the NEON consortium organised two public workshops, focused on sharing knowledge of European community funded projects, investors and stakeholders already active in mainstreaming investments in energy efficiency interventions and renewable energy sources, drawing attention to suitable financial structures ensuring cost-effectiveness of the service offer and minimizing business risk for the involved

actors. The first workshop, “Sustainable investments in citizen energy communities” was organised on the July 19th, 2022 and hosted three Neon’ sister projects, RenOnBill, Sensei and En-Track. The second one, “Sustainable finance solutions for citizen energy communities”, was organised on October 25th, 2022, and involved GNE Finance-SENS, BDO and ènostra.

3.1 Private funding opportunities

3.1.1 Equity finance and self-financing

The first private financial structures that will be analysed are instruments of equity finance and self-financing. These instruments imply providing ownership rights to the source of financing, splitting risks between the funder and the subject/organisation receiving funding. It is important to underline that equity finance does not necessarily produce profits and therefore dividends. The following are examples of potential sources of equity finance:

- **Equity capital:** energy communities can be created in different legal forms (cooperative, non-profit organization, association, benefit corporation, consortium, partnership etc.). Some of these may offer shares of capital to be purchased by individuals – i.e., the members of the energy community – and together represents the equity of the organisation. Equity capital is a “long term debt” to community members that can be repaid in the future: cooperatives, B-Corp, organisations can buy back shares of capital from the members at the same price they purchased it. Shareholding implies voting rights, usually proportional to the number of shares held.
- **Profit:** self-financing may come by the use of profits of the activity of the legal entity managing the energy community. Find below some examples of profit distribution:
 - **Dividend:** dividend distribution is the easiest way to share profits among shareholders. Each EU country has its rules: for example, in some states, cooperatives can only distribute a limited amount of dividend, which are heavily taxed.
 - **Rebate:** in the cooperative scenario, rebate on the price of the services offered to members are the most widespread. A direct benefit to the members is counterbalanced by the inability to use profits for further growth. An interesting characteristic is that rebates can be conditional for specific categories of members, such as low-income or energy-poor households.
- **Investment funds:** these products aim at investing funds collected from individuals and corporate into medium/long-term risk capital of companies with high expected growth potential, to generate revenues for investors. The time horizon of projects supported by investment funds is, at least, five years and may be longer for patient capital like those from pension funds.

3.1.2 Debt Finance

Unlike equity finance, debt financing does not have a direct impact on ownership structure of the CECs. Three main drawbacks: energy communities in their early stage, even if formally constituted, may face difficulties to access debt market; interest rate (i.e., the price of capital) could be perceived as too high in relation to services offered; lenders may affect decisions of CECs towards more profitable services, to the detriment of environmental and social benefits. At the same time, the main advantage is maintaining ownership and formal control of services and interventions. Several examples of the financing services will follow:

- **Lease:** Leasing energy-related improvements, especially the use of tax-exempt lease-purchase agreements for energy efficient-equipment, is a common and cost-effective way for state and local governments (as well as commercial property owners) to finance upgrades and then use the

energy savings to pay for the financing cost. Leases often have slightly higher rates than bond financing. However, leases are a faster and more flexible tool than many other options, including bond financing, and are an important tool for public entities to finance improvements in their own buildings.

- **Soft loans** are loans with no interest or below-market rate of interest. They may also have lenient terms, such as extended grace periods, in which only interest or service charges are due, or interest holidays. Soft loans are often used by states, regions, or local authorities to encourage investment supporting energy policies. They are often complementary to subsidies of fiscal incentives and go with coaching and technical support attached.
- **Energy Efficient Mortgages (EEMs)** encourage energy efficiency offering a better rate or increasing borrowing capacity, to buy an energy-efficient house or to cover the cost of refurbishments or deep renovations. For an EEM program, state and local governments typically engage via credit enhancement, such as an interest rate buy-down or loan loss reserve.

EEMs give property owners the opportunity to finance cost-effective, energy-saving measures as part of a single mortgage. The mortgage can allow a repayment period between 15 to 30 years, thus amortising the costs of the energy efficiency improvement over time. Property owners can secure an EEM at the time that they purchase a home or refinance their existing mortgage¹.

- **Revolving loan facilities** are credit instruments issued by financial institutions to provide the borrower with the possibility to withdraw, repay, and withdraw again. Revolving loans are a flexible financing tool, with flexible interest rates and allow individuals and companies to borrow money as needed for funding operational expenditures. These are pools of capital from which loans can be made for clean energy projects—as loans are repaid, the capital is then reloaned for another project. Assuming that defaults remain low, revolving loan facilities can be "evergreen" sources of capital that are recycled over and over again to fund projects well into the future. State and local governments can establish revolving loan facilities to support both their own energy upgrades (i.e., internal), and those in private sector (i.e., external).
- **Sustainability-linked loans** may incentivise borrowers to achieve ambitious and predetermined sustainability objectives. Performance is measured via sustainability targets, including KPIs, external ratings and equivalent metrics. These loans may be cheaper for CECs since, depending on how the borrower meets sustainability KPIs, the rate may fluctuate.
- **Green bonds** are debt instruments issued by an organization for the purpose of financing or refinancing projects with positive impacts on the environment. Funds are collected from the bond holder to the bond issuer. Green bonds are hardly accessible by single CECs, because of low size and excessive risks for investors, basket bonds pooling together multiple projects may be a solution.

3.1.3 Other forms of financing

1

The mortgage industry is an essential player in efforts to tackle climate change through its funding of the home renovation programmes needed to improve the energy performance of the EU's building stock. Therefore, the European institutions promote this type of instrument: since its inception in 2015, the EU Horizon 2020 funded the Energy Efficient Mortgages Initiative (EEMI) for the growth of a new, integrated, multi-stakeholder energy efficient mortgage ecosystem. For more information: <https://bit.ly/3CdPNrl>

- **On-bill financing and on-bill repayment programs** provide two options for property owners to pay for investments in clean energy upgrades through their utility. While electric utilities and natural gas companies typically run on-bill programs, there is an opportunity for state and local governments to capitalise on new on-bill loan funds and/or provide credit enhancement for existing on-bill funds. Depending on the programs available in each jurisdiction, some government entities may also be able to take advantage of on-bill programs to finance projects for their own facilities. On-bill financing allows the utility to incur the cost of the clean energy upgrade, which is then repaid on the utility bill. On-bill repayment options require the customer to repay the investment through a charge on their monthly utility bill as well, but with this option, the upfront capital is provided by a third party, not the utility. Additionally, on-bill repayment allows for a streamlined process as utilities already have a billing relationship with their customers, as well as access to information about their energy usage patterns and payment history. In some on-bill repayment programs, the loan is transferable to the next owner of the home or building.
- One of the potentially most interesting private funding schemes for energy-related projects such as NEON is **crowdfunding**. Crowdfunding is a funding scheme that relies on capital collected from many private investors (both individuals and corporates) through an online crowdfunding platform. Examples of crowdfunding are:
 - **Equity crowdfunding**: investors are rewarded with the dividends generated by the supported company (or project). This solution is particularly of interest for projects to be realised at a small and medium scale, like in the case of the creation of energy communities, i.e., a group of citizens and small businesses acting jointly to self-produce energy from renewables. Structure is similar to a direct investment, where the lender becomes the substantial owner of a determined share of the entity, or the project financed. Due to the ownership and administrative rights that are associated with the shareholder status, more rigid controls are generally performed to prevent fraudulent behaviours.
 - **Loan crowdfunding** (or peer-to-peer lending): it has some elements in common with the typical loan structure. In fact, after having reached the capital requested, the reimbursement plan foresees the payment of a core capital component and an interest component, at rates which are usually higher than those applied by the financial institutions.
 - **Profit-sharing / revenue-sharing**: the community project can share future profits or revenues with the crowd in return for funding now.
 - **Hybrid models**: offer businesses the opportunity to combine elements of more than one crowdfunding type.

Crowdfunding schemes are becoming a **feasible alternative to classic loans and mortgages in financing energy-related projects**.

3.2 Financial schemes within the NEON project: examples and best practices

One of the most interesting financial schemes within the NEON project is that of **Energy Performance Contracting (EPC)**. EPC is a form of **innovative financing of energy efficiency investments, where the contractor gives a financial guarantee for the expected energy savings on a project**. An EPC is a particular form of contract because **remuneration is closely linked to the success of the interventions** carried out by the supplier that can focus on both the energy saving of the project and on the use of renewable energy.

The two most common types of EPCs are referred to as a shared savings or guaranteed savings model:

- **EPC-Guaranteed**: under an EPC arrangement, an external organisation (ESCO) implements a project to deliver an energy efficiency project, or a renewable energy project, and uses the

stream of income from the cost savings, or the renewable energy produced, to repay the costs of the project, including the costs of the investment. Essentially, the ESCO will not receive its payment unless the project delivers energy savings as expected.

- **EPC-shared:** the ESCO can provide financing, as well as project development and implementation costs, with the energy savings shared between the ESCO and the client over the contract period. In this situation, the ESCO is assuming both the technical and the credit risk (of the client), which can be of value to the client as it avoids the need for upfront capital costs, with ongoing payments to the ESCO based on the savings obtained.

FIG. 1- Third Party Financing with ESCO borrowing and TPF with energy-user/customer borrowing: summary of relations

Source: ECS 2003: <https://bit.ly/3t3QG32>

On October 25th, 2022, the NEON consortium organised a second public workshop, “Sustainable finance solutions for citizen energy communities”, which focused on sharing experiences, best practices, and key challenges in creating and developing renewable energy communities, with a focus on the economic sustainability of projects and financial solutions adopted to support building energy efficiency, renewable energy, and digital innovation.

During the event, speakers from SENS, BDO and ènostra among others presented examples of private funding opportunities and issues related to them.

Sustainable finance solutions for citizen energy communities - A NEON Project's workshop

SENS introduced Wattify, a crowdfunding platform that gives investors the opportunity to invest their money in real, sustainable energy projects and earn returns while supporting the issuers of the project. The tool aims at realizing sustainable impact projects and at the same time growing the returns for the private investor.

The platform can give a pro daily rate of the energy generated in the project and produces a token that can be translated into money (the return on your investment). Energy communities may benefit from

the use of this platform. For example, the citizens of energy communities and people who live around could invest in a project that improves the surrounding areas on a visual scale (an issue that is sometimes faced in energy communities). In the future, it could be possible to use the energy savings not only as money but also to pay micro-PPAs, and contracts to have a fixed rate of energy price.

BDO provided interesting insights on private finance solutions for citizen renewable energy communities. Generally speaking, as it has been analysed above, it is possible to obtain financing for renewable energy communities from the following instruments: grants/ EU funds; loans from the Public Sector; Private funding ESCOs; investors and banks; EE and TE Funds; crowdfunding.

The Grants/EU funds and Loans from Public Sector can be a good start to boost the energy efficiency project in an initial phase but is important to find some private investors or some other way to keep the project alive.

A possibility to finance a CEC is the ESCO acting as a Sponsor: the tariffs agreed between NEWCO and the consumers (off-takers) through the power purchase agreement (PPA) or other commercial agreement types, result in what is known as a win-win for both the consumers as for NEWCO. The former will not only position himself as a proactive agent in the energy transition process –even not having place in his property for installing RE but they will also achieve significant savings on its electricity bill. The latter will obtain a certain financial profit as which carries out the investment, financing, and O&M, ensuring the placement of the renewable energy produced to the consumers, thus obtaining a certain financial profit. Under this model, the consumers may act only as off-takers, outsourcing all the management and financing of the projects to the third-party ESCO.

Another example of financing opportunities has been provided by ènostra, a national energy cooperative, based on active participation and direct involvement of energy citizens, that develops collective power plants and delivers renewable energy to its members. ènostra aims at increasing renewable energy quotes in the national mix and contributing to energy transition involving energy citizens.

In order to finance an energy community, ènostra fixed the following requirements:

1. the creation of the juridical subject (small association, cooperation, non-profit organisation);
2. the obligation to pursue ESG goals, not profit (no return to their investment);
3. stability: the energy community has to take into consideration the fact that participants in CEC may leave the community at any time.

In the process of creating the energy community, ènostra first offers information and training activities to improve awareness of citizens. The following 5 steps are:

1. feasibility study and mapping of stakeholders: through this step it is possible to study all the costs, benefits, and how to finance the project. Also, it is necessary to find the balance between the power of the plant and the amount of energy needed;
2. engagement of territory and membership campaign;
3. legal consultancy and constitution of the juridical entity (association, nonprofit organization...);
4. installation of renewable plants;
5. registration of the community in the EC national portal and activation of a premium tariff.

4. Service cost structure

As it is well known, the energy transition requires greater involvement of citizens, institutions and local companies in energy projects carried out at the municipal level through the development of energy communities. The aim is to ensure that these projects also provide social, economic, and environmental benefits that have an impact at the local level, achieving greater acceptance of these actions. However, in the current economic structure, in addition to establishing the social and environmental bases of the aforementioned energy transition, the citizen energy community must also show clear economic sustainability. To this end, it is essential to analyse and contrast the financing needs of the energy communities. Thus, the objective of this section is to show the financial needs of energy communities.

4.1 Characteristics and financial structure of ECs

Before proceeding with the analysis of the financing needs of ECs, it is worth mentioning that energy communities are an instrument that energizes the energy market at the urban level, through a more active participation of citizens as well as local companies and they contribute to the energy transition process. Moreover, energy communities have the following characteristics that have a considerable impact on the financial structure:

- They are a legal entity of voluntary and open participation controlled by shareholders or members who are individuals or legal entities (among others: associations, cooperatives, non-profit organizations, companies) and also local autonomous or national administrations. This aspect has a considerable impact on the financial structure of energy communities, since their essential principles and values make them entities with very different financial characteristics from conventional businesses or investments.
- Likewise, the main social objective of energy communities will be to offer energy benefits, from which environmental, economic or social benefits are also derived to their members or to the locality in which they operate, rather than to generate financial profitability. Therefore, even though financial sustainability is required, this basic principle allows the economic and financial activity of the CECs to be channelled in such a way as to allow a better use of resources.
- In addition to the aforementioned elements, the activities to be developed in the energy communities will be, among others, the generation of energy mainly from renewable sources, distribution, supply, consumption, aggregation, energy storage, provision of energy efficiency services, provision of recharging services for electric vehicles or other energy services. This vector, prioritizing the fundamental environmental and social pillars, allows energy communities to be used as technological tools to boost the energy transition, for example as aggregation or arbitrage elements, so that their financial structure is intrinsically linked to this activity.

Therefore, the new opportunities offered by the energy transition in which we are immersed generate the emergence of these new cooperation systems that promote a fairer, more efficient and collaborative system of our energy resources. Local energy communities offer an opportunity in this new framework and also allow a sustainable definition of their financial structure leading to the development of energy transition tools integrated into the economic system of society.

Within this structure, one of the most important factors is the cost structure. The cost scheme of an energy community is made up of several phases as shown in the following figure:

Fig. 2 – Cost scheme of an energy community

First, there are the costs associated with the communication and dissemination blocks, which also encompass the entire social engagement movement. This is not the most significant budget item, but it is the most valuable phase in terms of the nucleation of the energy community, since it is the phase where persuasion in the context of social and environmental awareness takes place. Second, there is the pre-design phase of the energy community where the fundamental pillar is the technical approach. However, it is crucial that this phase is synchronized with the social phase since the technical approach must reflect, in part, the social will. Third, there is the execution of the project itself. This is a parallel block to the execution of engagement. Finally, there is the management block. This fourth block encompasses not only the management of the energy community but also two fundamental elements: the integration of energy services and the medium and long-term projection of the energy community itself. In this section, each and every one of the above-mentioned blocks will be developed in detail.

4.2 Costs associated to the social phase: communication and dissemination

As developed in WP1, specifically in task T1.4, the social engagement methodology for the case of the creation and dynamization of energy communities is a key aspect. In the NEON project, six phases of engagement have been defined and are summarized below:

- **Phase 1: Awareness raising and recruitment:** identification of the channels and tools to recruit and raise awareness among participants.
- **Phase 2: Analysis of the pilot:** characterization of the pilots in its energy, economic, social and environmental aspects.
- **Phase 3: Promotion of the energy community:** planification of the legal, organisational and inclusion mechanisms within the Energy Community.
- **Phase 4: Creation of the leading group and collective ideation process:** empowerment of participatory workshops to codesign with existing/potential participants of the Energy Community, promote learnings and unite the group.
- **Phases 5 and 6 about constituting and implementing the CEC:** formal or bureaucratic steps needed, and the official launch

This structure can be visualized as follows:

Fig. 3 – Six phases of engagement

In addition to these phases related to the creation of the energy community, there is also a seventh phase related to the evolution of the energy community and its accompaniment. In these phases, the costs are mainly associated with personnel costs.

Finally, in this social phase, it is important to note that one of the costliest internal sub-phases of the social phase are the establishment of the primary objectives, the design and execution of the communication and dissemination process and the legal framework. The following figure shows an example of an outline of this structure:

Fig. 4 – Structure of the social phase

This planning is one of the pillars for the success of the energy community, so it is important to properly manage the resources used. Thus, for an adequate approach, it is crucial to contemplate a cost structure associated with the establishment of specific objectives:

- Compilation of success stories: presentation of key aspects for the success of real cases; standardisable material.
- Catalogue of typical technological solutions: this material is intended to guide the objectives and help in the initial decisions regarding the typologies of technologies that may be of interest for the fulfilment of the established objectives; standardisable material.
- Tools for analysis of technological solutions tailored to the specific case: these are simplified tools, programmed based on parameterised result sets, possibly with a visual interface in a web environment, standardisable tools.
- Technical support in the drafting of the project: the drafting of the project requires the involvement of a professional or a company qualified for this task that possibly are also eligible for subsidy.
- Financing plan: based on the technical project that determines the investment, the financing plan is drawn up. It is evaluated which part of the investment can be carried out with own funds, other sources of financing are identified, and it is decided which is the desirable route and which are the possible alternatives; susceptible to receive subsidies.
- Risk assessment of the project: to be able to seek funding, whether from the community members themselves, from a financial institution or from the public administration, a risk analysis needs to be carried out, socialised among the community members, and presented to potential investors or funders; susceptible to receive subsidies.

Finally, there are the legal dynamization aspects and how they fit into the energy community:

- Information kit - this material could have a content similar to the following: objectives of energy communities, typologies of communities, corresponding legal framework, stakeholders or who's who in your environment, step-by-step development, envision your community; standardisable material.
- Contact with mentors - provide a mentor from another existing and mature community to advise the developing community.

- Legal and administrative support - in the initial phase it is important to have this kind of support as the community needs to formalise its legal status; eligible to receive subsidies.

As observed, the following direct, indirect, and consumable costs are identified in the social phases:

- cost of personnel (generally qualified in sociological, communication and urban planning areas). This cost is associated with the inherent tasks of communication, dissemination and dynamization of this phase.
- cost of materials and consumables. These costs are part of the material used (and preferably recycled/reused) and its amortization.
- other associated costs: these would be the costs attributable to elements such as travel, rental or use of common spaces, rental or purchase of necessary audio-visual elements (which may be amortizable or acquired specifically for the project);
- subcontracting: in the case of needing support in fields such as legal, layout, etc., outsourcing is an indispensable tool when executing aspects of the social phase of the energy community.
- indirect costs: cost related not directly to the operation of the present phase.

4.3 Energy vectors, enabling technologies and costs associated to them

Both the pre-design phase and the execution and implementation of the energy community are based on the technological vector, so the most relevant technological aspects and their associated costs will be presented first.

4.3.1 Generation and energy vectors

When setting out the cost structure of the most technological tasks, it is crucial to first analyse the energy carriers as well as the renewable energy generation mechanisms. Thus, an energy community mainly manages two energy vectors: the electrical vector and the thermal vector. As for the suitability of energy generation technologies, the availability of local energy sources and the constraints of space and ease of integration into the built or buildable environment, whether rural, semi-rural or urban, must be considered.

In relation to this, in general, solar photovoltaic technology is highly adaptable to all types of environments, thanks to its modularity: it allows great flexibility of design and urban and architectural integration, and it is easy to install and involves simple maintenance. In addition, it presents a trend of significant reduction in all its costs and enjoys great popularity and media and social acceptance and has been the touchstone of the regulatory development of net balance first and self-consumption in recent years. In general, but especially in urban communities, it is the preferred technology in Europe and North America, even in latitudes with much less solar irradiation than the less sunny locations of Spain.

Fig. 5 – Solar photovoltaic technology

Another crucial aspect in the medium and long term in energy community environments is the vector of electro-mobility. Also in urban environments, electric mobility is called to be one of the keys to the energy transition, and as a solution to alleviate air pollution in large municipalities. There is growing concern about the impact of deteriorating air quality on the health and well-being of people, especially children and the elderly. It is to be expected, therefore, that the promotion and operation of charging points for all types of electric vehicles, as an infrastructure facilitating a benefit in terms of public health, is one of the aspects that could encourage the emergence of energy communities in cities.

Fig. 6 – Charging points for all types of electric vehicles

Another particularity of urban environments is building density, which in energy terms means a higher concentration of demand and shorter distances between consumption points; in this sense, another highly relevant technology is district heating (or heating and cooling) distribution networks. New generation district networks seek a higher degree of efficiency, through more efficient equipment, a reduction of individualized storage and thus associated thermal losses, and an exploitation of local and often unconventional means and resources (such as subsoil, groundwater, surface water or sewage water, waste energy, etc.). In Scandinavian countries, particularly in Denmark, district networks, much more common than in southern Europe, have been the basis for the configuration of energy communities since the late 1990s.

As far as rural areas are concerned, photovoltaic technology will also be very attractive and relevant, but we should not forget the different technologies for the use of biomass (forest or agricultural waste), such as gasification or direct combustion, anaerobic digestion of organic waste for the production of biogas, or wind turbines in those sites with sufficient wind resources.

Energy communities around agricultural and forestry residues can be promoted from the existing associative fabrics in some agricultural subsectors, with a strong cooperative tradition, such as the wine, nuts and olive oil sectors, or also from forestry consortia.

4.3.2 Enabling technologies

In addition to the energy vectors and aspects outlined above, there are also costs that are associated with enabling technology elements that are part of the energy communities.

This is a compilation of tools and technologies that have emerged in recent years because of the explosion of the information society and the growing social and economic digitalization we are experiencing and are part of the cost structure itself.

All the technologies that will be illustrated below are being explored from the Smart City approach as useful accelerators of a transition towards demand and supply models that allow for greater sustainability, i.e., greater efficiency, minimization of the consumption of non-renewable resources, use of new technologies and renewable energies, greater equity in access to services and greater democratization and inclusiveness in business based on the exploitation of publicly sourced resources and infrastructure.

- Data Science and data management platforms:** in today's technological and digital context, any aspect of personal or professional life generates a large volume of data, from internet browsing and e-shopping to finances. This data has become crucially valuable for any business or organization in terms of analysis and exploitable interpretation.

Data science or data analysis, known internationally by different terms (Data science, Big data or Data analysis) is currently a field of development and innovation that has revolutionized the approach to business models based on the provision of services, where the consumer is no longer a mere recipient of offers and purchase propositions, but with the provision of data on their conditions and preferences, it is the consumer himself who activates the creation of sales opportunities by service providers. Data science is today one of the most fertile fields in industry and economics.

Fig. 7 – Data management platform

Data science therefore owes its main argument to the emergence of a large volume of data, which must be organized and managed to harness the potential of a more consumer-driven buying and selling paradigm.

A Data Management Platform (DMP) is a centralized system for collecting and analysing large data sets from disparate sources, such as proprietary data (from an organization’s own applications, systems, websites, and products), as well as data from third parties and other partners. It is a popular tool in the marketing industry.

Data management platforms aggregate customer data from various sources and then analyse, organize, and segment it into different types of customers or 'audiences', analysing factors such as location, income, browsing behaviour, preferences, and past purchases.

More and more organizations are using data management platforms both to engage customers, partners, or supporters, and to formulate offers and continuous improvements tailored to the profiles of these customers, partners, or supporters.

The proliferation of the use and exponential growth of these platforms has led to the development of regulations on the protection of personal data, in an attempt to prevent fraudulent and/or criminal use of the data collected, as well as infringements of privacy and industrial or intellectual property rights.

Another common application of DMPs is the management of an organization’s purchasing, expenses, sales and billing. Energy service companies, for example, use such platforms to characterize the energy consumption of their customers, thus facilitating decisions on consumption savings and related expenditure.

- **Smart meters:** one of the primary sources of data for DMPs applied to energy monitoring and decision making are smart meters. A smart meter is a gas, water or electricity meter, capable of two-way communication (transmitting and also receiving information) between the consumer and the grid operator. The Smart Meter measures energy consumption in the same way as a traditional meter but has communication capabilities allowing the data to be read remotely and displayed on a device inside the home or transmitted securely outside.

Fig. 8 – Smart meter

They are placed at the supply boundary point, i.e., between the consumer's indoor installation (also called the consumer-owned receiving installation) and the distribution network connection, which is owned by the network operator.

The meter can also receive information remotely, e.g., to update tariff information or to change the type of consumption on a prepayment basis. This device provides updated information on the volume of gas or water and electricity that has been used in the relevant unit, either m³ or kWh. The information sent to the meter by the user or the company providing the service may include price information, connection or disconnection instructions, alarms, and instructions when there is wasted load, meter software update, date and time.

This has been accompanied by the effective empowerment of consumers to access their consumption data and the training to understand and manage it, an aspect that has raised numerous complaints from consumer organisations and from electricity distributors. The transfer of consumption data to third parties, not even with the consent of the consumers who hold the data, has also not been provided by the main distribution companies, making it difficult firstly for energy optimisation experts to analyse this data, and secondly, to propose measures to save on consumption and, therefore, on bills.

- **Sensors / Internet of Things (IoT):** in addition to data from energy meters, advances in electronics and sensor connectivity make it possible to imagine all sorts of devices that measure, process, and send data or commands over the internet. Sensors and other networked devices make up the now famous Internet of Things (IoT). Thanks to this technology, a company can collect vast amounts of data about the world, from pollution levels to noise levels, to make smarter decisions, in real time and from anywhere.

This hyper-connectivity, combined with advances in artificial intelligence, has led to the proclamation of the fourth industrial revolution, where each company's production process is monitored and documented with data collected through sensors. Real-time data is obtained and analysed to feed back into the production chain.

At the domestic level, all major appliance manufacturers are already developing smart versions of their products. For example, they are developing fridges with touchscreens, internet connectivity and cameras inside, capable of displaying recipes on the screen, warning about upcoming food expiry dates, ordering food that is out of stock from the nearest supermarket and playing music.

Therefore, we can understand the internet of things as a network of physical objects - vehicles, machines, appliances and more - that use sensors and interfaces and applications to connect and exchange data over the internet. In this sense, the internet of things is one of the sources of data providing management platforms and will undoubtedly be a technological field to be considered by existing and future energy communities.

- **Advanced residential demand-side management technologies:** probably one of the most important developments of the smart grid era are the numerous incentives that are pushing residential consumers to become active prosumers. Among the various concepts, explicit demand-side management coupled with "Smart Home" technologies seems to be the most interesting concept. This concept incorporates significant levels of customer participation, achieving

remarkable benefits, both qualitative and quantitative for the parties involved, as well as the electricity grids per se. In addition, demand-side management is expected to be channelled mainly to the energy market through newly introduced market players such as aggregators, energy communities and VPPs, which enriches their activities and establishes their role in the market.

Field sensor technologies typically integrate IoT elements such as those described above. The data obtained are supplied to these central engines that process the values obtained and try to obtain both the real comfort and the flexibility profiles that users have "offered" and are willing to have in exchange for better prices, facilitating explicit demand management campaigns by the distribution company or aggregator. Therefore, these tools generate "discomfort" functions to quantify and determine the maximum flexibility factor that can be considered acceptable.

In turn, and given that a large part of the demands satisfied are thermal demands and taking into account the great proliferation in recent years of elements generating heat/cold with electricity (different types of heat pumps), demand management can take into account the concept of Virtual Accumulation, using the inertia of buildings and potential thermal accumulation systems (DHW accumulators, among others) to manage the network.

- **Blockchain:** A blockchain is a digital contract that allows an individual party to perform and invoice a transaction (e.g., a sale of electricity) directly (peer to peer) with another party. The concept of "peer to peer" means that all transactions are stored in a computer network consisting of the computers of the supplier and the customer involved in a transaction, as well as the computers of many other participants in the network.

Traditional intermediaries are no longer necessary under this model, as the other participants in the network act as witnesses to each transaction between a supplier and a customer, and as such can also provide confirmation of the details of a transaction, because all relevant information is distributed throughout the network and stored locally on the computers of all participants.

- **Demand and social entrepreneurship:** the digitalisation of energy markets offers the possibility of repositioning the role of the consumer with greater empowerment, or at least more active participation, in different segments of the value chain. The position of the consumer can evolve from a merely passive role to a more active one, becoming a producer (prosumer), owning an electric vehicle and using it as a battery system compatible with their residence or workplace, benefiting from new contractual modalities based on demand management, or even sharing, transferring or selling surplus production within an energy community.

Consumers or prosumers can be understood as individuals, groups of people, households, small businesses, social enterprises, or local authorities, operating individually or in an organised manner, for example through associations, foundations or cooperatives. This vision gives greater weight to socio-economic and environmental objectives to the detriment of an exclusively profit-driven approach, without prejudice to admitting the participation of private companies with a legitimate profit perspective. It is under this vision that the focus on equity in access to energy emerges as a priority, and allows addressing solutions to alleviate dysfunctions of the current energy model as dramatic as energy poverty.

- **Techno-social trends:** to orchestrate a set of instruments that are effective today, it is interesting to highlight some facts that differentiate the current landscape and that are likely to be accentuated in the increasingly changing environment that awaits us in the future. Obviously, the citizens addressed are not the same as 20 years ago. Looking at socio-economic trends we see a certain paradigm shift. Citizens expect a personalised service and a good user experience: effortless, intuitive, fast but reliable. Millennials lead this kind of expectation. Digitalisation plays a key role in this and is increasingly "invading" wider spheres of everyday life. One of the ways of approaching user involvement is the so-called "gamification", as more and more people are looking for enjoyable and fun ways to encourage involvement and learning. In this way, the classical approach of an excessively technical or technological discourse is losing ground in favour of the use of psychology and neuroscience.

The last decade has created a new need: the need to be connected. It is not only about being connected everywhere and all day long, but also about being connected with multiple devices to multiple platforms. In other words, being connected to "everything" everywhere, 24 hours a day. And this is where digital technologies come into play: IoT, personal devices (terminals), networks, clouds, etc.

On the other hand, we observe a strong emergence of the collaborative economy. It is becoming easier, cheaper, and more efficient to involve a wider range of participants in value creation. New services and new business models are being created on the basis of collaborative work.

Mobility patterns are changing because of an increase in demand, but also as a result of an increase in supply, both in quality and connectivity of public transport and in the range of technological options. In this changing environment, mobility as a service is moving from a theoretical concept to an increasingly present reality.

4.3.3 Technological cost structure

All the elements and vectors mentioned and described above have their own associated costs (scaled to the corresponding magnitude), which are broken down as follows:

- Personnel costs: these are the costs associated not only with engineering but also with manufacturing, assembly, transport, installation, verification, and validation.
- Material costs: the costs of equipment and system elements.
- Operating costs: the costs inherent to manufacturing, assembly, installation, etc. in terms of energy, amortization, water consumption, etc.
- Subcontracting: in the case of needing to contract specific services, these should be considered in the items corresponding to subcontracting. Especially services with a cost of qualified personnel and/or integration services.
- Indirect costs: costs that are not associated with the execution and operation of the system itself.

These costs are found in a modular form both in the pre-design phase and in the execution of the project. Thus, in the pre-design phases, only material costs and operating costs will be incurred in the case of specific prototypes, but in the case of the implementation phase, all cost groups will be included.

In addition to the cost breakdown, it is important to consider the following aspects in the execution phase:

- financing aspects: these aspects include a range of options, from the participation of the public administration (central or local) in the investment, subsidies to cover part of the investment, soft credit through a specific line of credit tailored to local energy communities, reduction of taxes and/or duties such as the personal income tax of the participating citizens, reduction of VAT applicable to the material and/or services;
- supplier selection: i.e., advice on evaluation of tenders or facilitating the evaluation criteria;
- management platform: depending on the profile of the community and the technologies used, there may be different needs for management tools. It would be very useful to offer standard and free solutions for use by the communities (i.e., standardisable tools);
- risk control: it is advisable to continuously monitor any budgetary deviations at this stage.

4.4 Costs associated to community management

Finally, we have the cost structure of the energy community management. The following cost vectors should be considered in this management:

- **community governance and management of the operation:** the management of the community's activity during the operational period include corporate and economic management, maintenance tasks, etc. Possible support would be to compensate the toll for the use of the distribution network;
- **control and monitoring:** surveillance of results, verification of compliance with objectives and communication with members to socialise results and influence change in behavioural patterns are necessary;
- **continuous evaluation and improvement:** it is advisable to continuously monitor opportunities and risks as we operate in a changing environment;
- **development of new initiatives:** based on identified opportunities, or on new objectives or needs, new initiatives can be developed.

Especially with regard to the management of new initiatives, it is important to emphasize the need for integration of energy services. These energy services can be managed and implemented mainly by ESCOs or other entities. The associated energy services will be primarily aimed at achieving energy efficiency with the following two elements:

- **energy audits:** elements that will allow, firstly, to know the energy status of the facilities and secondly, to design actions to improve energy efficiency such as improving lighting, coatings and insulation of the facilities or the design of the methodology for the change of habits of human beings;
- **procurement based on energy efficiency:** as seen in task 2.2, there are procurement mechanisms based on energy efficiency such as the EPC and the P4P, which should be considered in the improvement of the energy efficiency of the energy community.

All these elements of efficiency improvement, have mainly three costs associated with them (depending on the services that are implemented):

- **personnel costs:** costs that are directly associated with the professional or non-professional paid work in the improvement projects raised;
- **indirect costs:** costs not directly attributable to the operation of the improvement project;
- **subcontracting costs:** costs that are generally directed to the hiring of experts or companies specialized in the subject matter of the improvement project prop.

5. Analysis of gaps between financial needs and actual financial instruments offer

Looking at the structure of costs and of potential financing schemes available, a set of issues for raising private finance arises, defining a gap between financial needs and actual financial instruments offer. Some of these are listed below:

- **Economic viability:** the lack of economic return for the stakeholders in the energy community and for society in general in implementing financial supporting schemes for the uptake of energy efficiency or renewable energy solutions could affect the decision. At the same time, the poor spread of specific financial products/services adapted to both energy efficiency and “energy poverty” (for example soft loans, on bill payment, on tax payment) and the lack of guarantees for debt repayment can keep market players from tackling certain operations.
- **Financial viability:**
 - **Commercial viability and analysis of counterparty risk of the consumers (clients):** long-term commercial agreements such as PPAs or other types with main consumers in the community will facilitate higher amount of private financing to be raised, as long-term visibility in the revenue stream will be achieved. Also, there could be longer tenors of the private debt, reducing the annual amount to be reimbursed and therefore anticipating savings gains for the consumers.

Moreover, counterparty risk of the (main) consumers should be analysed. The lower the average counterparty risk, the higher the amount of private finance that might be raised, as financial cushions for covering from non-payment risk will be reduced. Might be interesting to have one or some public sector consumers (or others) to increase financing appetite for the private financing of the Energy Community CAPEX needs.

Indeed, the following factors hinder private financing: debt aversion (even if they qualify to take a loan, low-income households tend to be reluctant to do so); long payback times (investors are wary that the savings achieved will not justify the cost of the energy retrofit), lack of confidence and trust in actual energy and economic savings associated with investments for this kind of measures; fear of incapacity of repayment, which could result in disconnection from the community; uncertainty of DR economic flows associated with reduction in consumption.

- **Detailed, reachable/robust business plan:** a detailed business plan must be created, including CAPEX needs, technical solutions with tested technologies, timeline for reaching the Operation Date, Income streams based on the future agreements and/or existing regulations (self-consumption by consumers of the community, surplus into the grid, others), O&M costs, including asset management, insurances, administrative costs, and tax and accountant treatment.
- **Technical solvency:** technical solvency of the sponsors, stakeholders, and/or subcontractors. Some barriers to the development of integrated energy services in energy communities, and to the organisation of CECs themselves, may be constituted by more technical issues. The availability of cheap domestic central energy sources can influence this kind of investments; the fossil fuel

dependence for a certain geographical area can be a strong incentive for the creation of energy communities based on the implementation of renewable energy sources, but if an area has easy access to cheap energy sources it could be a barrier. A related aspect is also the individual ownership of renewable energy production systems such as photovoltaic panels: in a country like Italy where many individuals own photovoltaic panels, the creation of energy communities and a consequent implementation of integrated energy services is harder to appreciate. Indeed, previous experience with the same technology, building, managing, and operating similar renewable energy projects.

Depending on the size of the CAPEX / Project, the financial solvency of the sponsors, stakeholders, and/or subcontractors might be also relevant. Indeed, the following factors represent potential barriers to raising private finance: lack of knowledge about existing financial supporting schemes; lack of capacity to undertake the bureaucratic work associated with traditional financial supporting schemes; lack of expertise (skills & training) and highly qualified specialists.

- **Legal viability and Security Package:** legal structure in place should permit pledge on shares (or similar holding instrument), assets, and/or credit rights arising from commercial agreements (e.g., PPAs or other commercial contracts with the consumers, rights to sell the surplus to the grid, ...). Existing regulations are compatible with private finance security package needs and enforceability. Indeed, the lack of standardisation of contracts underlying both funding and implementation of energy communities and their services constitutes an actual and potential obstacle to the development of this type of initiatives. Other factors that should be considered are: poor policy for energy efficiency/renewable energy investments (tax incentives, facilitation of administrative permits, lack of standardisation); low flexibility for implementing some measures; administrative and policy barriers.
- **Robust financial results adapted to updated market conditions:** financial results of the business plan must be in levels according to market conditions for private debt and equity from private investors.
- **Size of the Investments needed:** depending on the size of the investment needed and other factors (e.g., consumers, stakeholders, sponsors, ...) different private finance solutions will be available. Small projects under 3 million euros tend to be financed through crowdfunding, full equity, or leasing agreements with banks. Bigger sizes permit more sophisticated approaches with EE / TE debt and/or equity funds including project finance loans or project bonds with longer tenors.
- **Combination of public and private financing:** if this is the case, financial viability might be not reachable only using private financing, therefore a proper mix of public grants or loans and private funds, might be the proper solution, reducing the cost of capital.

ESCO – financing gaps

As deeply analysed in D2.2 (multi-actor energy performance contracting), the EPC concept successfully applied in several projects profiles but there is still room for improvements when considering it in the context of energy communities and integrated energy services.

The complexity of the energy balance has an important role in this context. In fact, when we talk about contracts related to guaranteed savings, they result successful when applied to a service where the energy balance is not complex. A simpler energy balance shows up when the different energy vectors do not

interact and, above all, the consumption pattern is very predictable. Moving away from these ideal conditions, the contracting process becomes more complex and more costly. One important cost is the high fixed cost that reduce the possibility of working with small projects. The high costs condition the ESCOs to look for bigger projects, with volumes of more than 300,000 euros.

The cost problem makes difficult for “distant” company (without local presence or interest in the territory) being interested in these projects. This gap will be further analysed in the guidelines presented in the following section.

The involvement of public sectors becomes crucial to test and promote new forms of collaboration, such as PPCP (public administrations, private companies and local communities’ partnerships). Schemes like these may facilitate the implementation on new integrated services as well as new renewable energy communities and related energy contracting elements.

Another key role is played by aggregators, representing a vehicle to aggregate and group up several physical and virtual communities in order to build up their standing in energy negotiations, contracting and funding and financing processes. At the same time, aggregators are fundamental to ease the integration of ESCOs.

The financial materiality of sustainability aspects (e.g., renewable energy, air quality, energy poverty or social cohesion) implies that considering these factors in financial schemes and models allows reduce risks and to mitigate costs for members of the energy communities (i.e., reduction in the cost of energy, reduction of tolls for a reduced use of the transport network, reductions of costs related to oil and gas, etc.)

Large commercial and industrial facilities may benefit from economies of scale factors, with a clear and defined structure involved, and exploit schemes such as the chauffage one (see D2.2). On the contrary, due to the complex financial structure and a not well-defined risk and revenues profile, energy communities face more difficulties in applying usual EPC schemes.

The next chapter is therefore aimed to identify business risk for energy communities and its distribution and minimization, to therefore offer some guidelines in this regard (see Chapter 7, Conclusions).

6. Guidelines for business risk distribution and minimization

6.1 Energy efficiency investment risks

It is possible to identify different risks and uncertainties that could endanger the successful implementation of energy efficiency and energy services projects also in the context of energy communities and reduce [profitability](https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/engineering/profitability)²: as such, they must be taken into account by financial institutions when it comes to the evaluation investments’ risk.

² <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/engineering/profitability>

Risk factors can be classified into the following categories according to their conceptual characteristics: (a) borrower-specific (BRW), (b) sector and project-category specific (PSRS) (c) country-specific (CSR), and (d) project-specific (PSR).

Creditworthiness of the borrower, which is the only BRW risk factor, depends on the creditability of the applicant for the loan/ financing, being either a physical person or a company/ legal person. PSRS risk factors depend on the project's sector. CSR risk factors depend only on the country that the investment takes place. Finally, the PSR risk factors depend on the ad-hoc characteristics of each project irrespectively of all the aforementioned ones.

The main risk categories and how they are categorized will be explained below. This section takes into account the analysis conducted by Diamantis, Kleanthis, Flamos, Karakosta, & Doukas (2022) and in the Triple-A project (2020).

The *financial risk* category encompasses the default risk. It is characterized by the factor “creditworthiness of the borrower” which indicates the financial capacity of the borrower to pay off his debt and is of paramount importance from the financial institution's point of view, since it is usually the determinant factor for deciding whether a loan must be given or not. Another type of financial risk is the pipeline risk that is related to the reliability of promoters to deliver on their prospected pipeline. The financial risk category also encompasses the currency risk. Currency risk typically signifies the risk of loss associated with fluctuating foreign exchange-rates. Exposure to foreign currency investment can present a significant risk for investors

The second category, *behavioural risk*, depicts behavioural biases of end-users regarding how they consume energy, and it comprises the “rebound effect”, a specific behavioural bias that can be classified as a PSRS risk factor. It affects the end-user and mostly emerges when the implementation of an energy efficiency project leads to an increase in the energy demand, compared to what is the case before the energy efficiency measures' implementation. As a result, the actual energy savings may be significantly lower than the projected ones.

The third main risk category addressed in the literature as the riskiest one, is the *energy market and regulatory category*. This category includes the “energy prices and taxes volatility” and the “request for issuing project permits” factors that can be classified as CSR risk factors. Energy prices and taxes volatility is associated with the price risk in energy efficiency investments. On the one hand, the uncertainty about energy prices influences the decision to undertake an energy efficiency investment as it may lead to unexpected monetary savings and therefore the return of the energy efficiency investment may differ from the initial estimation. Furthermore, energy taxes are considered important as they affect the end-use price and thus the monetary savings of the energy efficiency investments. The request for issuing project permits signifies the legislative complexity for the completion of a project (e.g., construction permits/licenses, protocols, or other approvals under the provisions of law), which could lead to administrative risk in a specific country. The administrative risk could be a decisive factor for the selection of a country to implement a project. Some instances of this risk factor are the request for issuing project permits/licenses for renovations of existing buildings, the installation of geothermal heat pumps, the change of the electromechanical equipment, etc.

The *economic risk* category reflects the macroeconomic environment of the country in which a project is implemented in. Therefore, this category is connected to the “weak economic environment”, i.e., the poor economic conditions that may exist in the country in which the energy efficiency investment takes place. It is connected to, among other indicators, interest rates, inflation, availability of finance, etc. These risk

factors can be classified as CSR risks. Weak economic environment can negatively influence the investment in many ways, such as affecting the investment's profitability through inflation or KPIs through interest rates. It should be noted that the economic category is also connected to other more specific risk factors (e.g., interest rates volatility) that are part of the weak economic environment, as reported by literature.

Finally, the last category analysed is the *technological risk* category that refers to the technical aspects of the installed equipment and the skills of the involved workers. It is composed by different risk factors: the "technical complexity", a PSRS risk factor, the "low quality of initial savings assessment", the "implementation of low-quality equipment or poor project design", and the "inadequate O&M" which are all classified as PSR risk factors. It affects the chances for successful project implementation, by increasing the possibility that expected energy savings are not achieved. The implementation of low-quality equipment or poor project design refers to the equipment and design characteristics of the examined project. According to the quality of the equipment and the design, a level of technical risk can be defined. Inadequate O&M represents the uncertainty regarding the proper O&M of equipment. O&M is considered a crucial factor to achieve the expected energy savings. The low quality of initial savings assessment is associated with the capacity to predict accurately the expected energy savings, as well as to define properly the baseline energy consumption. Different practices are used for the estimation of energy savings, such as computational tools and simulation models from certified experts, empirical approaches and processes, and results from other similar energy efficiency projects.

6.2 Risk mitigation strategies in energy efficiency financing

Risk mitigation strategies help dealing with risks, by planning remediation activities for reducing their impact or probability of occurrence in the project. There are four main strategies to deal with risk: (i) "*risk reduction*" or "*risk elimination*", (ii) "*risk transfer*", (iii) "*risk absorption*" or "*risk acceptance*", and (iv) "*risk avoidance*". The first strategy aims at decreasing the impact or probability of occurrence of risk by applying specific measures, while the second strategy refers to transferring risk from one party to another (e.g., via insurance contracts). According to the third strategy, the impact of risk is acceptable, thus no actions are required for reducing it. The final strategy can be applied if the probability of risk's occurrence exceeds a present threshold, where in this case, the project should be aborted. Moreover, this strategy can be considered when risks with significant impact on the project occur and thus the project may be withdrawn, or its objectives may change.

The following are specific mitigation strategies related to the risks analysed before.

For what concern the financial risk category, the following mitigation strategies are suggested: project aggregation, loan guarantee mechanisms, off-balance sheet financing, grants, and subsidies. Specifically, in relation to the factor "creditworthiness of the borrower", it is suggested to carefully study the creditworthiness of the borrower and/or the ESCO in the negotiation stage. Credit ratings offer an evaluation of a prospective debtor's ability to pay back debt. This rating is a metric for comparing fixed-income securities. Companies are assigned a rating based on their financial outlook, past and current situation. The same holds true for markets as a whole that can be assigned ratings. Consequently, companies or markets with good credit ratings will have a reasonable level of debt, a good track record of paying it back, as well as a healthy earnings potential. For what concern the pipeline risk, investors should evaluate the certainty of the pipeline before committing to an investment. In relation to the currency risk, it will be important to assess whether project cash flows will be generated in a different currency than the one in which the investment is made. One method to safeguard against this risk is hedging to mitigate the impacts of undesirable exchange rate changes.

Concerning the behavioural risk category, it is recommended to consume energy in a more efficient way. Other suggestions concern energy taxes information provision, price regulation, subsidies and tradable permits, energy efficiency standards, ecotaxes, absolute caps, sustainability communication, design, evaluation and performance of policy, economic instruments, new business models, sustainable lifestyles, and consumer behaviour, raising awareness and promoting education in business, technology, and innovation.

For what concern both the energy market and the regulatory risk category, strategies may include fixed-price contracts and hedging (forward contracts, future contracts, swaps, option contracts and fixed-price contracts). Similarly, risk mitigation strategies related to economic risks include long term fixed interest rates and hedging.

Finally, strategies to mitigate technologic risks include: energy savings guarantees or insurances and diagnostics (in relation to the factor “low quality of initial savings assessment”), performance bonds or insurance equipment insurances, insurances required by the law and diagnostics (in relation to the factor “implementation of low-quality equipment” or “poor project design”), performance bonds or insurances, diagnostics, standardized M&V processes (in relation to the risk factor “inadequate O&M”).

7. Conclusions

Since 2019, the EU legislation provides unprecedented recognition and support for the role that ECs can play in transitioning to a just, sustainable economy. In this context, private investments play a major role as across the EU, most of the financing for ECs is channeled through them³.

The analysis conducted in this report outlined a variety of valuable private funding instruments available to ECs, suitable for supporting the creation and the development of renewable energy communities. In particular, crowdfunding represents one of the potentially most interesting private funding schemes for energy-related projects such as NEON.

Furthermore, the report highlighted the potential barriers to secure financing from private financiers. In addition to financing needs of ECs, investment risks require special attention.

In view of these findings, a set of guidelines for business risk distribution and minimization is presented in the following table.

Energy efficiency investment risks	Risk factors and their classification	Risk mitigation strategies
Financial risk category		Project aggregation, loan guarantee mechanisms, off-balance sheet financing, grants and subsidies

³

	Creditworthiness of the borrower - BRW	Careful study of the creditworthiness of the borrower and/or the ESCO in the negotiation stage
	Pipeline risk	Evaluation of the certainty of the pipeline before committing to an investment
	Currency risk	Assess whether project cash flows will be generated in a different currency than the one in which the investment is made Hedging
Behavioural risk category	Rebound effect - PSRS	Consume energy in a more efficient way Other strategies: energy taxes information provision, price regulation, subsidies and tradable permits, energy efficiency standards, ecotaxes, absolute caps, sustainability communication, design, evaluation and performance of policy, economic instruments, new business models, sustainable lifestyles, and consumer behaviours, raising awareness and promoting education in business, technology and innovation
Energy market and regulatory risk category	Energy prices and taxes volatility - CSR Request for issuing project permits - CSR	Fixed-price contracts, hedging (forward contracts, future contracts, swaps, option contracts)
Economic risk category	Weak economic environment - CSR	Long term fixed interest rate, hedging (forward contracts, future contracts, swaps, option contracts)
Technological risk category	Technical complexity - PSRS	

Low quality of initial savings assessment - PSR	Energy savings guarantees or insurances, diagnostics
Implementation of low-quality equipment or poor project design - PSR	Performance bonds or insurances, equipment insurances, insurances required by the law, diagnostics
Inadequate O&M - PSR	Performance bonds or insurances, diagnostics, standardized M&V processes

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